

Annex 1: Theory of photon reassignment super-resolution

Photon reassignment technique can be seen as a variant of structured illumination microscopy in a point scanning regime¹. Each through-the-pinhole image of the sample is positioned in a given position of the camera with a determined separation s and a de-magnification M ². The signal recorded by the camera $I(\vec{x}_s, \vec{x}_d)$, with spatial coordinates \vec{x}_s, \vec{x}_d (respectively for sample and detection coordinates) can be written as:

$$I(\vec{x}_s, \vec{x}_d) = \iint H_e(\vec{x}_0) U(\vec{x}_0 - \vec{x}_s) H_d(\vec{x}_0 - \vec{x}_d) d^2 \vec{x}_0, \quad (1)$$

where H_e corresponds to the excitation PSF, H_d the detection PSF, and U the field scattered by the sample.

Eq. 1 considers that the sample is displaced in order to create an image. However, in our case, the illumination beam is scanned over the sample. This can be done mathematically by changing the coordinates $\vec{x}_s = -\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_d = \vec{x}_2 - \vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_0 = \vec{x} - \vec{x}_1$ in Eq. 1, obtaining:

$$I(\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2) = \iint H_e(\vec{x} - \vec{x}_1) H_d(\vec{x} - \vec{x}_2) U(\vec{x}) d^2 \vec{x}. \quad (2)$$

If the detector is extended enough with a large sampling capability as compared to the pinhole image size, pinhole weight factor can be neglected. If we further introduce a demagnification factor M to reassign point $\vec{x}_r = (1-M)\vec{x}_1 + M \cdot \vec{x}_2$, the reassigned image can be written as:

$$I(\vec{x}_r) = \iiint H_e(\vec{x} - \vec{x}_r - M \cdot \vec{x}_d) H_d(\vec{x} - \vec{x}_r - (M-1)\vec{x}_d) U(\vec{x}) d^2 \vec{x} \cdot d^2 \vec{x}_d. \quad (3)$$

The optical transfer function (OTF) of the optical system $C(\vec{k})$ with spatial frequency coordinates \vec{k} can be described as:

$$C(\vec{k}) = C_e[(M-1)\vec{k}] C_d[M \cdot \vec{k}], \quad (4)$$

where C_e and C_d are the excitation and detection OTF. In the fluorescent case, the difference in the wavelength between light excitation and emission (Stokes shift) has to be included at this point. However, in the RCM case, there is no wavelength change and C_e and C_d are identical and can be described, in the ideal case, as a disc function.

$$C_e(k) = C_d(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k \leq k_0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

with $k_0 = 2\pi/\lambda$, λ the wavelength. It can be observed that the radius of C_e is delimited by a factor of $1/(1-M)$. So, the maximum radius of the support in the OTF depends on the de-magnification factor M . Sheppard² and Dubose et al.³, have shown that the maximum cut of frequency for the OTF can be expressed as:

$$k_{\max} = \frac{k_0}{1-M}. \quad (6)$$

Where it can be observed that the support of the OTF can be doubled in the frequency domain when the de-magnification of the system $M=1/2$ (so equivalent to a rescan amplitude factor of 2) leading to a doubling in resolution as compared to regular RCM.

Annex 2: Nanomaterial imaging

90 nm diameter silver nano-rods (Blue Nano, USA) with 10's of micron length have been imaged with rescanned-RCM. The sample has been spin-coated on a coverslip and immersed in oil-immersion refractive index matching medium.

Figure 6: Silver nano-rods observed by (a) Regular RCM, (b) re-scanned RCM. (c,d) Zoom in the selected area of the *a,b*, (d) Line-out on *c,d*.

The extracted diameter of the rods (91.2 and 92.6 nm in Fig. 6 matches with the supplier measured diameter of 90 ± 5 nm.

References

1. Xu, N., Liu, G. & Tan, Q. Adjustable super-resolution microscopy with diffractive spot array illumination. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **116**, 254103 (2020).
2. Sheppard, C. J. Super-resolution in confocal imaging. *Optik* **80**, 53–54 (1988).
3. DuBose, T. B., LaRocca, F., Farsiu, S. & Izatt, J. A. Super-resolution retinal imaging using optically reassigned scanning laser ophthalmoscopy. *Nature Photonics* **13**, 257–262 (2019).